

The FOSS GIS Workbench on the GFZ Load Sharing Facility compute cluster

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Compute Clusters

- A set of loosely connected computers that work together
- which can be viewed as a single system

Benefits over single computers of similar speed:

- performance increase
- no availability constraints
- more cost- and energy-effective

GFZ High Performance Compute (HPC) Cluster

Cluster GIS Workbenches

Benefits for geocomputation tasks

Parallelization

Deployment of tasks with long duration

Resource intensive tasks

Secure and stable environment

“sorcerers apprentice”

“fire and forget”

“size matters”

“Murphies law”

Geographic Resources Analysis Support System (GRASS) GIS

A Geographic Information System (GIS) is needed, able utilize the cluster environment, providing a sufficient degree of user friendliness to allow for wide application.

- .Largest and oldest Free and Open Source Software GIS
- .> **300** modules + user contributed extensions
- .Support many databases
- .Scripting: Shellscript, Python, Perl, etc.
- .Well documented, large user community
- .Compatible with various cluster environments

GFZ HPC/LSF GIS Workbench:2008

Compute Cluster:

- 32 nodes, each with a 80G drive
- 2 TB fileserver
- Gigabit Ethernet Network
- SUSE Linux Enterprise 9
- **Load Sharing Facility (LSF)** queuing system

Pilot installation of GRASS 6.3:

- Command line interface
- Graphics to be displayed offline

```
GRASS GIS  
Welcome to GRASS 6.3.0 (2008)  
GRASS homepage: http://grass.osgeo.org/  
This version running thru: Bash Shell (/bin/bash)  
Help is available with the command: g.manual -i  
See the licence terms with: g.version -c  
Start the GUI with: g.gui tcltk  
When ready to quit enter: exit  
GRASS 6.3.0 (mdv_data):~ >
```


GFZ HPC Cluster: 2012

Load Sharing Facility (LSF) queing system

234 nodes [2008: 32 nodes] / 480 CPU / 3084 cores

5 Tbyte Ram

19 processing queues

Suse Linux Enterprise 2011

GFZ HPC/LSF GIS Workbench: 2012

GRASS 6.4.2

- Access via Shell and TclTk-GUI
- 3D visualization: NVIZ / Paraview
- Dedicated modules to distribute GIS workload on the cluster
 - within GRASS session
 - external scripting.
- Up to 3084 parallel GIS (theoretically) jobs possible

The road ahead

- Additional GUI (wxpython)
- Individualized add-on repositories
- GRASS 7.0 (development branch)
- **Integration of desktop and cluster-based processing (GRASS/QuantumGIS)**

Application: Tsunami Mapping

The first task was the mapping of simulated tsunamis (“Virtual Tsunami Atlas”) for the TRIDEC Project (www.tridec-online.eu). For this, up to 400 processing nodes were used.

**Tonight:
Poster XY552**

Application: Long term processing

- .Geometrically complex/challenging simulation data sets
- .Significant amounts of processing time per node required
- .Worst case so far: 20 full CPU days for a single data sets**

Application: Globe Maps

Map canvas (GRASS GIS)

Georeferencing

Integration data / backdrop maps

Merging of color spaces

Globe Rendering (POV-Ray)

Atmospheric effects

Camera effects

Rendering

Application: Globe Map Animations

Visualization of spatio-temporal behaviour for simulated tsunami waves for QC.

Many timeslices to be computed (GRASS), and rendered (POV-Ray).

Rendering images to be **merged into a animated film.**

Steps 1 -3 have to be done for many simulations.

Globe Map Animation Example

Tsunami Animation:

- .Up to 750 still frames per globe animation
- .Linear processing: ~ **1 week**
- .Parallel processing: << **0.5 day**

Example: Maximum waveheights of the Tohoku 2011 Tsunami

- .4 * 750 = **3000 Renderings**
- .Multiple Iterations

Conclusion: A LSF-based HPC GIS Workbench

A **research utility** in the sense of “**Software as a Service**” (SaaS)

A first step towards building a **GFZ corporate cloud service**.

Allows to tackle GIS tasks previously out of reach of conventional workstations.

High performance geocomputation becomes available for an audience beyond conventional HPC / Grid power users.

Thank you !

